

**INGLIZ TILINI O'RGANISH JARAYONIDA NOFILOLOGIK
YO'NALISHDAGI IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN TALABALARNING KASBIY
KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TA'LIM KLASTERINI JORIY QILISH
USULLARI.**

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Annotasiya Ushbu maqolada jismoniy imkoniyati cheklangan talabalarga ingliz tilini o'rgatishda til materiallarini birgalikda o'rganish samaradorligi hamda talabalar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalari va tanlangan usullarning samaradorligi haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Hamda maqolada O'zbekistonda pedagogik ta'lim soxasi uchun ta'lim klasteri muhitida nofilologik yo'nalishdagi imkoniyati cheklangan talabalarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish metodologiyasiga e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Nofilologik yo'nalish, imkoniyati cheklangan, kasbiy kompetentlik, ta'lim klasteri, metodologiya, til materiallari, nogironlik, tinglab tushunish, gapirish, yozish, o'qish.

**МЕТОДЫ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО КЛАСТЕРА В
РАЗВИТИИ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ СТУДЕНТОВ С
ИНВАЛИДНОСТЬЮ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.**

Аннотация В данной статье представлена информация об эффективности совместного изучения языковых материалов при обучении английскому языку студентов с ограниченными физическими возможностями, а также результаты исследований, проведенных студентами, и эффективность выбранных методов. Также в статье акцентируется внимание на методологии формирования профессиональной компетентности студентов с ограниченными возможностями по нефилологии в условиях образовательного кластера для сферы педагогического образования Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: Нефилологическая направленность, инвалид, профессиональная компетентность, образовательный кластер, методика, языковые материалы, инвалидность, аудирование, говорение, письмо, чтение.

**METHODS OF IMPLEMENTING EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER IN THE
DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS WITH
DISABLED IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE.**

Annotation This article provides information about the effectiveness of joint learning of language materials in teaching English to students with physical disabilities, as well as the results of research conducted by students and the effectiveness of selected methods. Also, the article focuses on the methodology of developing the professional competence of students with limited opportunities in non-philology in the environment of the educational cluster for the field of pedagogical education in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Non-philological orientation, disabled, professional competence, educational cluster, methodology, language materials, disability, listening comprehension, speaking, writing, reading.

INTRODUCTION

Innovative approaches to the practice of learning foreign languages, in particular, English, which is considered a leading tool in international communication, in world educational

institutions, based on the needs of language learners, based on the need for professional and life needs, implementation of the principles of teaching disabled students in the field of non-philological education based on individual and mixed educational technologies done Systematic work is being carried out to improve the methodology of rapid development of emotional-expressive speech based on the mnemonic base while learning the English language without taking into account its grammatical aspects, training competent personnel of the international standard.

Today, the legal normative bases for training modern personnel who know several foreign languages, conducting scientific research on learning foreign languages, and improving language teaching methodology are being created. The introduction of the English language educational cluster in the development of professional competence of students with limited opportunities in non-philological fields remains relevant.

Regularly holding sports competitions among persons with limited physical abilities and disabilities in special educational institutions and neighborhoods;

formation of a modern material and technical base for people with limited physical abilities and disabilities to engage in sports in all types of sports educational institutions.

As we all know, today, as we all know, the revival of sports and foreign languages, namely the English language, remains an urgent problem. Because learning English is a modern demand, it is a language not only for physically healthy people, but also for those with physical disabilities. It is our highest goal that our Uzbek Paralympian champions can express their opinion fluently in English in the world arenas. [1;3-4-p] Also, in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development of foreign languages, organizational measures for the study and popularization of foreign languages in accordance with the decision No. PD-5117 of 19.05.2021, as well as paragraph 7 of the decision in order to ensure the implementation of this decision mainly to create conditions for the development of students' basic language skills (listening, reading and speaking, writing), including by connecting foreign language departments of higher education institutions to ensure students' in-depth study of foreign languages;

Introduction of internationally recognized methods of teaching students foreign languages and assessing their knowledge (formation of language skills in students with disabilities), including wide use of distance and other modern forms of education in the educational process, and other teaching subjects in a foreign language.

By mastering at least two foreign languages, the potential of students to expand their world view and increase their competitiveness in the labor market. [2] For this purpose, we base the following on learning foreign languages for students with disabilities at the University of Physical Education and Sports. Formation of skills in nasology of disabled students from language materials.

1. Formation of listening and speaking skills in visually impaired students
2. Formation of reading and writing skills in hearing impaired students.

Nowadays, as we all know, the revival (optimization) of sports and foreign languages, especially the English language, remains problematic. Because learning English is a modern requirement, it is not only for physically healthy people, but also for those with physical disabilities, to create skills by teaching them language materials, to know the terms of their specialty in English, and of course, to express their opinion in English fluently in the world arenas. This is our highest goal. As a result of our study of extensive scientific and methodological works, there is almost no information about the mechanisms of applying the methods of English language teaching in the course of training of students with disabilities. It should be noted that the lack of

scientifically based recommendations for teaching listening, reading, writing, and speaking in terms of sports that correspond to the training process of students with disabilities determines the relevance of the chosen direction of work. [18; 2-3 p].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of the research is to study the theoretical and practical aspects of developing the professional competence of non-philological students with disabilities in the environment of the educational cluster.

The tasks of research: analysis of the theoretical basis of personal interest and pedagogical activity in students' development of speech based on the mnemonic base of professional communication;

improvement of motivational, cognitive, technological, socio-communicative and reflexive criteria of indicators of rapid development of gesture-based speech in English based on the mnemonic base in non-philological students;

improvement of the model of rapid development of students' communication in English based on the mnemonic base;

to develop a methodology for rapid development of emotional-expressive speech based on hand movements in students based on a mnemonic base and to base its effectiveness on experience.

RESULTS

Research and analysis of scientific and methodical literature, pedagogical observation, pedagogical control, pedagogical testing, analysis of training process with disabled people, pedagogical experience, mobile application were used.

In Uzbekistan, the problem of training qualified personnel for the field of pedagogical education is observed together with the formation of new socio-cultural, economic and political conditions, changes in the tasks, conceptual rules, content and structure of higher education. Today's higher professional education in Uzbekistan allows to shift the main attention in the educational process from the paradigm of knowledge acquisition to the formation of professional competence in future specialists. In this case, the knowledge of foreign languages in educational and scientific-methodical literature of foreign educational and scientific-methodical literature plays an important role in obtaining information on a wide range of theoretical and practical issues, communicating with colleagues in foreign countries. It can be seen that foreign language is a means of acquiring new professional knowledge and improving skills for specialists of pedagogical higher educational institutions. [2;45-50p, 5;78-82p].

The priority task of teaching a foreign language should be the formation of professional competence of students in a foreign language, in particular, teaching them to understand authentic texts devoted to various theoretical and practical issues in a specific field of training. It is recognized that the content of the technologies used in the publications devoted to the problems of teaching foreign languages in HEIs is not sufficiently developed. This is evidenced by the fact that the majority of students have poor knowledge of professional vocabulary and difficulty in translating specialized texts related to the field. It should be mentioned that at the current stage of the development of higher education in the non-philological direction, as a result of the increasing volume of information and the acceleration of the educational process, the importance of innovative technologies based on the competence approach of modular teaching, modular teaching, business and role-playing games, "operant education" is increasing in the use of computer language didactic tools. . According to the data, when the innovative technologies used

in the educational process have a targeted pedagogical effect and there are appropriate material and technical conditions, the effectiveness of the formation of professional competence of higher education students is significantly increased. They form the desire to study, intellectual potential of a person, active educational and cognitive activity [3;32-38p, 4;88-92p].

DISCUSSION

The problematic situation under consideration reflects the existence of a serious disparity between today's demand for professional foreign language competence of students of HEIs in the field of pedagogy and the level of understanding of meaningful authentic text in a certain direction. All of the above is the reason to consider solving this imbalance as an important task and emphasizes the importance of theoretical development and practical justification of innovative technologies used in language teaching.

Today, the main factor of training a competent specialist is not imparting knowledge, but formation of basic competencies; teaching universal methods of activity; it is to teach the basic concepts of how the field of activity is structured, the norms and rules of professional-practical activity [7; 62-65p, 9; 55-59p].

A graduate of higher education institution should understand not only the existence of special knowledge, skills and abilities, but also the importance of foreseeing personal-professional, self-development in the professional activity of his choice. Given that setting professional goals is a key indicator of success, special attention should be paid to students' mastery of goal-setting technologies. Thus, the modernization of the educational system of our Republic sets new quality requirements for the technology of specialist training in higher educational institutions in the field of physical education, sports and tourism, pedagogy and psychology, special pedagogy. As the main paradigm of the modern educational cluster, modern conceptual rules of the traditional methodology of the educational process, specialists who meet international standards, tools and methods of formation of professional competence of students of higher education institutions and, most importantly, the concept of beneficial cooperation of subjects of pedagogical education are put forward. The condition of the educational cluster should be understood as the pedagogical (teaching) environment at the intersection of the common goal of the learner, the teacher, and the social actor (institution, parents or substitute persons, authorities, foreign partners). In the context of an educational cluster, not all subjects need to meet at the same time and place. It is necessary to ensure that their common goals intersect, that is, beneficial cooperation. Otherwise, an environment of a pedagogical innovative educational cluster will not be created.

In the conditions of the educational cluster, the educational content based on the competence approach makes the setting of professional goals relevant as the main indicator of students' acquisition of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies provided for by the third generation State educational standards, and helps to successfully form an understanding of the high level of basic competencies allow the structure, norms and rules of the future field of activity..

CONCLUSION

In short, the opinions about competence and the competences that are intended to be formed and developed in students on the basis of their views on this matter differ from each other according to their tasks and essence. innovative technology of foreign language teaching aimed at personal and professional development, the "operant education" method and determining the rating in the study group, educational multimedia presentation, use of the Internet, role-playing games, the author's English-Uzbek profession a dictionary of terms and a teaching manual in English with

authentic content related to the field, it is intended to use the methodology for assessing the professional competence of students in a foreign language.

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